

**RE-CREATING THE CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE
SOCIAL NETWORK OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES IN STUDENTS'
FREE TIME.**

Yuldashev Dilshod

ESL teacher at “General philology” department at
Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: This article explores possible benefits of social media for education and how we can implement tasks through social networks. The article suggests using Social Media as a part of the lesson but in class time but rather after-or-pre class time by allocating them in specific groups or chats. Uzbekistan has been taken as desired context to implement the suggested method of teaching through social networks.

Key words: Social networks, The English language, classroom environment, students’ spare time, Telegram, Facebook, Uzbek learners.

We are living at the crossroads of history where it is so much hard to imagine or predict our future without the impact of social network and its role in education. Although the social networks, firstly, were denied or were not supported by the majority of educators/academic institutions, they are being implemented and used as one of the main parts of the current lessons since their huge advantages and comfortability over any other means of messaging tools. Even some of the academic settings are designed to teach their classes through these social networks, that said Telegram, WhatsApp, Facebook, Skype and etc. All of them can help teachers to design and freely rely on their superiorities to other tools that can be used in lessons, to illustrate in Uzbekistan most educational institutions and private sectors of teaching as well are moving towards using Telegram, this is because of following reasons:

a) Telegram is the one social network in Uzbekistan that is widely used by many Uzbek people in all communities and a large number of the unconfirmed news on any

subject goes easily viral on this social media, messages on Telegram messenger are circulated across the Uzbekistan. [1]

b) Telegram is now a new paradigm between social networks and instant messengers. Telegram is very popular and growing rapidly in many countries such as Iran, Uzbekistan. [2]

However, many public institutions are restricting the use of mobile phones or social networks in education settings due to their approximate danger in teaching processes also they are accepted as main distractors while teaching/learning momentums. Considering these measures, it would be better if teachers suggest or implement the use of social networks after or pre class time so that students will not be distracted by them. The suggested and recommended way would be as follows:

1) The usages of social networks help students to learn and study more time independently, in order to learn a foreign language autonomously, creativity is required for imagining virtual spaces for learning. [3] Independent study skills are absolutely crucial nowadays because during the lessons, students may not comprehend and get the whole topic and it requires additional learning processes, which is autonomous learning. While doing autonomous learning processes, students will have to use social networks to get more resources and outside help from others so that they can set clear directions towards their goals, which is learning subjects.

2) Allocating or implementing the social networks to students' studies is not enough if they are not assessed through those networks. To do so, teachers will have to create specific tasks of assignments that can help teachers to track students' learning and their willingness to continue using social networks. Spending some adequate time on social networks is absolutely important to them especially young generation prefers to compare their pace with their counterparts all the time, whenever they learn any new feature of social networks it is so easy to show and teach other with those kinds of newly discovered items/features. These new ways of learning things not only about the world related knowledge but also any specific subject related information can be used

in these ways. Besides, these things can enhance students' creative skills while using new things on their own with the same purposes. Adding to the examination of the environmental and individual dimensions of creativity, it demonstrates that being situated within a community of creative individuals could enhance creativity. [3] Students feel more content if they know that they are going to be checked in some ways or with some milestones and this can impact on their willingness to try and work harder with the knowledge that they are getting through social networks.

3) Moreover, students may have more free time that can help them to learn a new language but current young generation are addicted to social networks to much that nothing could replace the role of mobile phones or computers. These new gadgets mean so much to them that they carry their smartphones wherever they go with them. Considering the potential danger, we, as teachers and parents, can change or add some possible benefits, that said, if they want to use their phones for surfing the Net, we can add subject related or educational purposes. But here teaches come the first place because they are the creators of the topics, tasks and they should be responsible with the curriculum or agenda of the subjects. So teachers will find one of the most preferred social networks to use in students free time to engage in their educational goals.

Online learning provides various instructions and appropriate timings or tasks given by the lecturers so that students will have to follow those instructions to get to the next levels. Instructions can be synchronous (communication where participants interact in the same time space as video conferencing, zoom, google meet, and WebEx) or asynchronous (time-separated communication such as e-mail, google form, streaming video content, posting lecture notes and social media platforms) [4].

In the synchronous type of learning, students actively participate in learning processes whether asking questions if they have any misunderstandings or give feedbacks about the topic learnt in time. This might be quite useful for them because there is a person who is controlling everything in online class and that person can answer the questions of the participants. Although this type of learning is beneficial if

learners are learning a new language because learning a new language is quite challenging especially for the starters who have just started learning, but it has also some drawbacks, such as learners may not be able to find right time to attend the classes. The reason why many people prefer to study online is because they work or study in other places and it is certain barrier for them to engage in a new language or they may skip some classes and eventually it might even cause to stop learning a desired language.

In the asynchronous way of learning, it can offer some more advantages to the learners of new languages, to illustrate you do not have to spend or allocate specific timings, you can do it wherever you have time, after the studies/work or before studies/work. It means that the person who chooses the asynchronous type of learning cannot be distracted or bothered with daily-life matters, such work/study related task or problems. In turn, this type of learners may have less stress in their life because everything gets in their own places without mixing or confusion. But this type of learning has also some disadvantages, for example if a learner does not understand the theory of the topic, that person will have to ask it through emails, or texts which mostly causes delaying in learning processes because it takes more time to message and get replied soon.

Taking everything into consideration, learners use social networks in their day-to-day lives and adding the educational purposes to their uses of social networks could show potential benefits in their education, particularly learning a new language.

Reference:

1. Kodirova, H. (2021). Speech Act Analysis of Telegram Messages on Coronavirus: Social Media and Fake News in Uzbekistan. *Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu.uz)*, 8(8).
2. Hashemi, A., & Zare Chahooki, M. A. (2019). Telegram group quality measurement by user behavior analysis. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 9, 1-12.

3. Chik, A. (2017). Learning a language for free: Space and autonomy in adult foreign language learning. In *Space, place and autonomy in language learning* (pp. 44-60). Routledge.

4. Simamora, R. M. (2020). The Challenges of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: An essay analysis of performing arts education students. *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, 1(2), 86-103.